

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Sakari****FIRST NAME: Faustina****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used Zotero to insert references.

The author used MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. The following statements on paraphrasing are correct except one.

- The author cannot just change a couple of words and rearrange the sentence structure.
- The information that the author is providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote.
- The writing style used to express the author's ideas must be different from the author's style.
- It is not a must to cite the work the information came from.¹**

2. When doing research, it is advisable to do the following except.

- Ask a question worth answering.
- Find reliable evidence to support your reasons.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University), 8.

Find an answer that one cannot support with good reasons.²

Draft a report that makes a good case for your answer.

3. **Which of the following is a correct in-text citation?**

(Gladwell 2000 64–65).

(Gladwell 2000, 64, 65).

(Gladwell 2000, 64–65).³

(Gladwell 2000, 64 and 65).

4. **The following are statements on steps in reviewing and analyzing the literature. Which one is not correct?**

Extract and record information by asking systematic questions of the literature.

Develop an analytic format and use it consistently.

While analyzing the specifics, broader themes and issues can be omitted.⁴

Write a short overview report on each piece of literature reviewed, including specific detailed information.

5. **In writing conclusions, one should not do the following.**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2008), 18.

³ Ibid., 129.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg; Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Massachusetts: Sage Publications, 2008), 51.

- Restate your answer to the question.
 - Introduce new information or ideas in conclusion.**⁵
 - Re-summarize the main points.
 - Include a final, broad statement.
6. **In the WHO style guide, headings are used to ensure the consistency of and provide clarity in a publication by indicating the hierarchy and structure. Which of the following statements is not true?**
- When preparing a manuscript for publication, keep a record of the font type and size used for each heading level.
 - The number of heading levels can be three or more.**⁶
 - Numbered headings are obligatory in the WHO Technical Report Series and may be used in other publications if warranted.
 - No full point is required for headings or chapter titles.
7. **The following cases are considered plagiarism except**
- Using the exact words of the author.
 - Using data that the author has compiled through his/her independent investigation.
 - Using information from the author's work that is regarded as common knowledge in the discipline.**⁷
 - Reproducing in your paper a chart contained in the author's work.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 3.

⁶ WHO, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: WHO, 2004), 12.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 9–10.

8. **Which of the following is the correct way of documenting a reference list for a journal article consulted online using author-date style?**

- Kiser Lisa J. 2011. "Silencing the Lambs: Economics, Ethics, and Animal Life in Medieval Franciscan Hagiography." *Modern Philology* 108, no. 3 (February): 323–42. Accessed September 18, 2011. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/658052>.
- Kiser, Lisa J. 2011. "Silencing the Lambs: Economics, Ethics, and Animal Life in Medieval Franciscan Hagiography." *Modern Philology* 108, no. 3 (February): 323–42. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/658052>.
- Kiser, Lisa J. 2011. "Silencing the Lambs: Economics, Ethics, and Animal Life in Medieval Franciscan Hagiography." *Modern Philology* 108, no. 3 (February): 323–42. Accessed September 18, 2011. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/658052>.⁸**
- Kiser, Lisa J. 2011. Silencing the Lambs: Economics, Ethics, and Animal Life in Medieval Franciscan Hagiography. *Modern Philology* 108, no. 3 (February): 323–42. Accessed September 18, 2011. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/658052>.

9. **For the WHO style guide, Citations can be inserted in the text using either the Harvard system or a numerical system. Which of the following statements is true?**

- The Harvard system shows the author and date in the body of the text.⁹**
- The Harvard system is preferred as it is obligatory for the WHO Technical Report Series.
- With the Harvard system, the references are numbered as they occur in the text.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 130.

⁹ WHO, 24.

- In the citation, the number is given in italics and placed in parentheses in the different point sizes as the text.

10. **Latin term *ibid* is used to shorten a citation to a work cited in the immediately preceding note. Which of the following statements is correct?**

- If the citation includes a page number, a comma must be placed after *ibid*.
- Do not use *ibid*. after a note that contains more than one citation.
- Avoid using *ibid* to refer to footnotes that do not appear on the same page.
- All the above.** ¹⁰

¹⁰ Kate L. Turabian, 99.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. F. *Completing Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Massachusetts. Columbia University. Sage Publications, 2008.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: WHO, 2004

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.